

Structural and Thermal Analyses of Manganese Oxides

M. G. BODAS, H. V. KEER* and A. B. BISWAS

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology,
Bombay-400076

Manuscript received 11 March, 1974 ; revised 4 October 1974 ; 11 December 1974

In a systematic investigation on dependence of properties on preparative conditions and sintering, structural and thermal (DTA/TGA) analyses of three different samples of MnO_2 , heated at 400° , 600° , 750° , 850° and 1050° for several hours, have been reported here. Room temperature X-ray analysis indicates that pyrolysis of $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 250° and a natural ore from Mysore fields yield tetragonal $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$, while electrolytic sample from Japan is orthorhombic $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$. DTA/TGA showed that $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$ transforms to $\alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3$ and then to Mn_3O_4 at 590° and 935° respectively, while the corresponding phase transitions in $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ take place at 550° and 935° respectively. Further, a broad endothermic hump in DTA of both $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$ and $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ and was observed from 30° - 150° with a minimum around 50° . Since TGA shows no mass loss in this temperature range, the anomaly is believed to correspond to a solid-state transition. Besides, the temperature variation of the dielectric constant of $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$ exhibits a maximum around the same temperature ; therefore the DTA peak may be associated with ferroelectric $\rightarrow$ paraelectric transformation.

A general correlation between structural and thermal properties has been made.

MANGANESE dioxide is an important chemical both from fundamental and technological points of view. It occurs in various crystalline forms and finds extensive applications in battery manufacture. Although the numerous forms of MnO_2 have been studied by several workers, there are wide discrepancies between the results obtained. Kanungo and Sant¹ have recently reviewed the available data for MnO_2 and its thermally generated products, mainly Mn_2O_3 and Mn_3O_4 . A thorough literature survey revealed that neither a systematic investigation on the structural and physical properties of MnO_2 has been made nor any correlation of the available data attempted. Besides, no satisfactory explanation for the origin of an endothermic peak in DTA of MnO_2 around 50°C has been offered. In the present communication, the details of the X-ray and thermal (DTA/TGA) analyses of MnO_2 and thermally generated products have been given and a correlation of the results has been made.

Experimental

Samples of MnO_2 were selected from three different sources :

(a) Pyrolytic product obtained from $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck, Germany ; purity 98.9%) by heating at $\sim 250^\circ$ in air for several hours.

Fig. 1—Differential Thermal Analysis of-(A)- $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$ (Prepared from $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$)(B)- $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ (Electrolytic MnO_2)

Fig. 2—Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis of-(A)- $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$ (Prepared from $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (B)- $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ (Electrolytic MnO_2), (C)-Natural Pyrolusite ore

(b) Electrolytic MnO₂ (made in Japan, purity 90%).

(c) Natural pyrolusite ore (from Mysore fields, purity 60%).

These samples were sintered at 400° (48 hr), 600° (48 hr), 750° (72 hr), 850° (48 hr) and 1050° (48 hr) followed by either annealing or quenching in air.

Room temperature X-ray diffraction analysis was performed using CuK_α radiation (λ = 1.5418 Å) filtered through a Ni foil. DTA and TGA curves were recorded from room temperature to 1100° in static air (Fig. 1 and 2). The rate of heating was ~ 10°/min. Calculated lattice parameters are listed in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

X-ray analysis: The samples from pyrolysis of Mn(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, electrolytic MnO₂ and natural pyrolusite ore shall be designated as A, B and C respectively.

Unsintered samples A and B were found to be β-MnO₂ and γ-MnO₂ respectively. On heating these at 400°-850° and 1050° respectively, α-Mn₂O₃ and Mn₃O₄ were formed.

Sample C sintered at 400° was found to be tetragonal and the X-ray data resembled with the reported one³ for MnO_{1.88} (nonstoichiometric β-MnO₂). On sintering at 600°, orthorhombic symmetry (≅ ramsdellite, R-MnO₂) results. This is an unusual observation and the lowering of symmetry may be due to the reaction of impurities with the oxygen absorbed by MnO_{1.88}. On sintering at 750°, α-Mn₂O₃ is formed.

Thermal analyses: In DTA curve of sample A a hump was observed from 30°-150° with an endothermic peak at ~ 50°. The two other endothermic peaks at 590° and 935° correspond to phase transformations β-MnO₂ → α-Mn₂O₃ and α-Mn₂O₃ → Mn₃O₄ respectively. Similarly in a sample B a hump was observed from 30°-150° with an endothermic peak at ~ 50°.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DATA OF MANGANESE OXIDES

Temperature and duration of sintering	MnO ₂ prepared from Mn(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O A	Electrolytic MnO ₂ B	Natural pyrolusite ore from Mysore fields C
Room temperature (unsintered)	—	Orthorhombic	Tetragonal (Main component MnO ₂)
Prepared at ~ 250°	Tetragonal a = 4.42 Å c = 2.85 Å	—	—
400° in air for 48 hr. and furnace cooled	Cubic a = 9.32 Å	Cubic a = 9.41 Å	Tetragonal a = 6.87 Å, c = 7.07 Å
400° in air for 48 hr. and quenched to room temperature	Cubic a = 9.32 Å	Cubic a = 9.40 Å	—
400° in dry oxygen for 20 hr. and furnace cooled	Cubic a = 9.38 Å	Cubic a = 9.38 Å	—
600° in air for 48 hr. and quenched to room temperature	Cubic a = 9.32 Å	Cubic a = 9.23 Å	Orthorhombic a = 4.47 Å b = 9.38 Å c = 2.82 Å
750° in air for 72 hr. and quenched to room temperature	Cubic a = 9.37 Å	Cubic a = 9.41 Å	Cubic a = 9.39 Å
850° in air for 48 hr. and quenched to room temperature	Cubic a = 9.35 Å	Cubic a = 8.59 Å	—
1050° in air for 48 hr. and quenched to room temperature	Tetragonal a = 5.74 Å c = 9.41 Å	Tetragonal + Cubic a = 5.84 Å, c = 9.38 Å and a = 8.39 Å	—

The endothermic peaks at 550° and 935° correspond to phase transformations $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2 \rightarrow \alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ respectively. DTA of natural ore sample did not show any phase transformation in the whole temperature range of study due to presence of inhomogeneity and impurity.

TGA of sample A gave no mass loss upto $\sim 460^\circ$, then abrupt loss in the range $460^\circ\text{-}575^\circ$, no loss from $575^\circ\text{-}850^\circ$ and then again loss beyond that temperature (Fig. 2). The two losses observed correspond to phase transitions $\beta\text{-MnO}_2 \rightarrow \alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ respectively. The theoretical mass losses calculated for these reactions correspond to the compositions $\text{MnO}_{1.5}$ and $\text{MnO}_{1.36}$ respectively. The discrepancy in the experimental and theoretical values is presumably due to the presence of small amount of adsorbed water ($\sim 1\%$) which is not observed in TGA curve due to lack of high resolution.

In sample B there is no mass loss upto 50° , a continuous loss upto $\sim 590^\circ$, then an abrupt loss upto $\sim 650^\circ$, no loss upto $\sim 1000^\circ$ and then again loss beyond that temperature. The continuous loss from $50^\circ\text{-}590^\circ$ indicates that the original sample of B is $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ and oxygen is gradually lost in this temperature range. However, this change in composition probably proceeds without any alteration in structure upto a certain stage (attained under equilibrium conditions at 400° after which it (structure) suddenly changes to that of $\alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3$. Incidentally, the corresponding abrupt loss in mass in TGA is shown up belatedly at 590° , since the rate of phase transformation at 400° is perhaps slow while the rate of heating is comparatively fast. The mass losses in the ranges $590^\circ\text{-}650^\circ$ and $1000^\circ\text{-}1050^\circ$ correspond to the transformations $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2 \cdot x \rightarrow \alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\alpha\text{-Mn}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ respectively. The experimental loss in the temperature range $30\text{-}550^\circ$ corresponds to the theoretical mass loss for $\text{MnO}_2 \cdot 0.3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (theoretical 5.8%). Therefore, in $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2 \cdot 0.3$ mole of water per mole is believed to be present. The (mass) losses in the temperature ranges $30^\circ\text{-}650^\circ$ and then upto 1050° correspond to the molecular formulae $\text{MnO}_{1.55}$ and $\text{MnO}_{1.36}$ respectively. Therefore, it can be presumed that adsorbed water molecules ($\sim 5\%$) are present in $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ upto 550° .

Origin of endothermic DTA peak in $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$ and $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ in the temperature range $30^\circ\text{-}150^\circ$

Although thermal decomposition of $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$ and $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ has been studied by several workers, there is no satisfactory report pertaining to the origin of an endothermic DTA peak in the range $30^\circ\text{-}150^\circ$. This

peak is probably due to a ferroelectric to paraelectric transition in MnO_2 . This view is confirmed by the work of Bhide and Damle^{3,4,5}. Their observations may be summarized briefly as follows :

"(1) The dielectric constant (ϵ) of MnO_2 is high ($\approx 10^5$) and shows a maximum around 50° .

(2) Curie-Weiss law, $\epsilon = A/(\tau - \tau_c)$ is obeyed above 50° .

(3) Hysteresis loops were observed in MnO_2 below 50° . Above this temperature the loops disappeared.

(4) Typical butterfly loop was observed in MnO_2 when biased with increasing fields.

The ferroelectric behaviour may be due to interaction of permanent electric dipoles, which rotate freely in the paraelectric state. If this be the case, then $A \approx 3 T_c = 969^\circ\text{K}$ (theoretical). However, the experimental value of ϵ at 60° is $\sim 2 \times 10^5$; therefore, $A \approx 2 \times 10^6$. This large discrepancy indicates that the origin of ferroelectricity is not due to the presence of permanent dipoles. Thus a suggestion can be made that the ferroelectricity in MnO_2 may be due to a structural transition."

In both β - and $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$, Mn^{4+} ions are surrounded by distorted octahedra. It is possible that the displacement of Mn^{4+} ions towards one of the O^{2-} neighbours occurs giving rise to ferroelectricity. However, more searching internal structure investigations would be necessary to confirm this plausible argument.

Electrical conductivity measurements of these samples will be reported elsewhere.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the referee for the helpful suggestions. One of us (M.G.B.) is grateful to the Director, I. I. T. Bombay for the award of a junior research fellowship.

References

1. B. R. SANT and S. B. KANUNGO., *J. Sci. Ind. Res.* (India), 1972, 31, 264.
2. SAMPSON and WADSLEY. *Amer Min.*, 1948, 33, 695.
3. V. G. BHIDE, R. V. DAMLE and R. H. DANL., *Physica*, 1959, 25, 579.
4. V. G. BHIDE and R. V. DAMLPE., *Physica*, 1960, 26, 33
5. V. G. BHIDE and R. V. DAMPLE., *Physica*, 1960, 26, 513